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EDEN Registry - Conceptual Model

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Abstract

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TERMINOLOGY

Important Note: in this document, we use the term 'repository' to broadly also include long-term archives and services associated with or supporting repositories and archives. There is a need for more specific definitions of these actors/ agents, and this is discussed in detail in the document.

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
BCDR	Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CPP	Common Preservation Package
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OAIS IF	OAIS Interoperability Framework
OAIS RM	OAIS Reference Model
PDI	Preservation Description Information
RDA TRSP WG	RDA Working Group on Trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers
TDA	Trustworthy Digital Archive
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

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Context

EOSC EDEN WP2 needs to establish a registry of repository characteristics that can be used for a variety of applications, including

- Selection of repositories by end users as a target for deposits, based on their own criteria.
- Mapping of repository attributes to one or more profiles based on an **attributes inventory**, for example determining which repositories publish adequate attribute lists for assessment by an authority, participation in a network or federated infrastructure, or which repositories meet the attribute profile of an aggregator.
- By design, allow appraisal of a set of repository attributes against a set of metrics, tests, and benchmarks, even if such appraisal is outside the scope of the EOSC EDEN project.

To enable development of such a registry, based on prior work and infrastructure developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, OSTRAILS, and the EOSC Data Commons projects, a conceptual framework needs to be established for the ecosystem, and the attributes and services associated with the actors/ agents in the ecosystem, while aligning with the frameworks developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC and OSTRAILS for assessment. This document provides an overview of the inputs available for development of such a conceptual framework.

The registry that is proposed for EOSC EDEN interacts with existing aggregating resources (e.g. re3data, FAIRSharing, and COAR) but there are good reasons for providing an additional service, discussed in more detail in the document.

Consideration also needs to be given to the ease of maintaining, extending, and updating repository attributes. This introduces several design aspects, for example:

- Using specifications such as FAIRiCat (tested in the FAIR-IMPACT project) to publish and maintain repository attributes locally while simplifying synchronisation with aggregating registries, including the EDEN registry, re3data, FAIRSharing, COAR, the EOSC Resource Hub, and any other interested parties.
- Ensuring that definition of new attributes, its associated metrics and tests, its facets for inclusion into search, discovery, and profile matching use cases, and its publication in local FAIRiCat implementations are all fully configurable in application data, allowing definition and operationalisation of new attributes without the need for coding.

The Scope of Conceptual Modeling

To implement a knowledge base with some form of associated assessment, one needs several conceptual model implementations. These are:

- A model to describe the 'Ecosystem': the entities (actors or agents, things, and concepts) and the relationships between them that describe participants in the workflows/ use cases associated with that ecosystem. These models are context-dependent: they are different for different ecosystems, even though some relationships and entities are shared between ecosystems.
- A model to define the relationship between characteristics of the ecosystem entities and some form of profiling, assessment, or comparison to expectations. Such a model (the 'Compliance Assessment Model') is generic, and applies to all ecosystems - although it may require some minor modification in some instances.
- A model to describe the Attributes associated with entities in the model: where they are authoritatively defined, how they are assessed, and how they relate to collections of attributes defined for a specific purpose by an actor in the ecosystem. Within this model, the TRSP Working group in RDA has started elaboration of Mechanisms of Assessment and Certification that may be of use and can be integrated if required.
- A model to define the Mechanisms of Aggregation and disaggregation of attributes. Some attributes are inherited by child entities from their parent entities, and some attributes are aggregated from child entities to parent entities.
- A model to describe the relationships between entities related to Guidance (best practices, standards, procedures, ...), which extends the Compliance Assessment Model.

Ecosystem Model

Entities and relationships between them are defined in a number of existing models, the most general of these being the [DCAT-AP](#) model and the [schema.org](#) model. There are also several sources for definition of standard relationships in knowledge organisation systems and in research data management or digital library context - including [SKOS](#), [OWL](#), and examples such as the [CODATA Research Data Management Vocabulary](#) and the [Semantic Science Integrated Ontology](#)¹.

Prior work in FAIRCORE4EOSC² and FAIR-IMPACT³ have made a start to define an ecosystem model for repositories (aimed at describing the ecosystems for semantic interoperability framework compliance assessment and FAIR assessment). The most elaborate of these is shown in Figure 1.

¹ Some of the pre-existing definitions will apply in more than one model context

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067253>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13486326>

Figure 1: Entities and Relationships for (EOSC) Framework Compliance Assessment

This model is not granular enough for our purposes in respect of the 'Repository/ Catalogue' entity, since this entity has additional nuances associated with it. The FAIR-IMPACT project analysed the additional granularity, defining additional detail as in Figure 4. The main objective of the analysis was to describe the levels of granularity of metadata and attribute information in the ecosystem.

Compliance Assessment Model

There are several models to be considered as inputs, these are mostly aligned with one another but further harmonisation and deduplication of terminology will be good. The models are

- The **Compliance Assessment Toolkit** conceptual model⁴, developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC, and forming the basis for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) developed in the project. It serves as the basis for PID Policy Compliance Assessment, and for work in progress in respect of FAIR assessment in OSTRails and in the EOSC Data Commons projects (Figure 2).
- In FAIR-IMPACT, a model was published to describe the relationship between attributes and the objects they describe, and how these translate into compliance assessment (Figure 3). This serves as an elaboration of the object and metric, test,

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067253>

but there is a wider set of comparisons in practice that do not necessarily involve validation by an authority⁶. Harmonisation of these two models, with a view to also accommodating the notion of a 'profile' (see Figure 4) as developed earlier in the EOSC EDEN project, will be a useful starting point for registry and eventual alignment or compliance assessment.

Figure 3: "A high-level representation of the relationships between entities involved in trustworthiness of a repository"⁷

The model defined in Figure 3 includes descriptions of the entities and their relationships, this is available directly from the reference.

⁶ More about this in the section on 'Mechanisms of Validation and Assessment'.

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058634>

Attribute and Assessment Mechanism Model

Figure 4 shows a provisional model for attributes and their relations to assessment mechanisms developed by the RDA TRSP WG.

Figure 4: Attributes, Profiles, and Assessment Mechanisms⁸

The attributes associated with a repository, which is the main focus of the EOSC EDEN project, are conceptually a subset of all the attributes (properties) associated with the ecosystem we are describing⁹. Within this large collection, we can define additional subsets of attributes that we refer to as a 'profile':

- A repository or a service to repositories can offer a subset of attributes using a number of approaches that are discussed in more detail in the next paragraph.
- Any number of additional subsets can be defined for a variety of purposes. For example, it may be that in order to participate in a network or federation, a subset of attributes must be available, or to be certified by an authority, a subset of attributes must be available for assessment¹⁰.

In practical terms, there are a number of profiles that we should document as a minimum (in effect tagging the master list of attributes defined by EOSC EDEN with profile identifiers or labels). See Appendix A for a more detailed discussion and a listing.

⁸ Work in progress by the RDA TRSP WG, [presented at Plenary 25](#).

⁹ We refer to this inventory of all attributes that are in scope as the 'Standard Set'.

¹⁰ There are likely several additional generic subsets that are not described in Figure 4 yet, and there will be many specific cases.

Attributes can be obtained from multiple generic sources, including

- **'Self-hosted'**, for example, attributes are available as broad-based metadata from a URL associated with the entity - using a number of standardised, machine-actionable approaches. Such approaches include the [FAIRiCat](#) specification, which was tested as a means of practical implementation in the FAIR-IMPACT project¹¹ and is strongly promoted as a simple and viable mechanism for sharing of repository attributes in a sustainable manner.
- **Registry-based dissemination**, for example by submitting and maintaining repository attributes in re3data, FAIRSharing, COAR, and similar registries. While these registries serve particular use cases well, they are often out of date since maintaining the information is not a priority for repositories, and adding new attributes usually requires modification to the registry implementations. The registries will benefit in time from self-hosted attributes, which enables periodic automated synchronisation of attributes between repositories and registries.
- **Authority-based dissemination**, which entails harvesting repository attributes from certification authorities. The benefit would be that the asserted value of an attribute has been independently verified. The approach has practical limitations at the present time since we are not aware of any authority that publishes verified assertions present in certification applications as machine-readable content¹². Moreover, the available data only applies to successful applicants, since unsuccessful applications are not published.

Annexure B discusses this aspect in more detail, based on work done in the RDA TRSP WG.

Mechanisms of Aggregation

A provisional model was developed in the FAIR-IMPACT WP5 to describe the levels of aggregation of attributes for digital objects, collections of such objects, repositories for such objects, and their relationships to registries and organisations. The model was not published and requires refinement, specifically in respect of

1. Registries are not part of a parent-child relationship involving objects, collections, and repositories and the organisations involved in providing services for these, but rather can be a source of information for any of these. A more refined definition of these relationships is required.
2. There are a number of terms that are often used interchangeably to describe the entities involved in providing broad-based resources to curate, preserve, and disseminate research outputs - including 'collections', 'archives', 'services', 'catalogues', 'indexes', 'repositories', 'registries' and so on. These terms need to be described properly, disambiguated, and the relationships between them defined.

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534285>

¹² CoreTrustSeal, for example, publishes its assessments in

Figure 5: Sources of Attributes and Mechanisms of Aggregation¹³

A refined model for the broad concepts and entities shown in Figure 5 is needed before any further definition of aggregation scenarios can be considered. Examples of such scenarios include (not comprehensive, there will be others):

1. **Unique instance aggregation:** An attribute of a child entity (for example the licence or metadata schema applicable to a research object) is aggregated as a unique list of occurrences to provide an attribute for a parent entity (e.g licenses supported by or metadata schema implemented by a repository or organisation).
2. **Numerical (domain) aggregation:** An attribute of a child entity is aggregated using a computational algorithm (Maximum, minimum, sum, average, mean, weighted average, ...) to obtain a single value for a parent entity. In some cases, a representative sample of values for child entities can be used, and this then also implies additional context for the aggregate value - certainty and variance based on sample size.
3. **Disaggregation - computational:** A characteristic of a parent entity is disaggregated to child objects on the basis of a computation. For example - storage costs that are only known for a repository can be disaggregated proportionally on the basis of dataset size to obtain an estimate for each dataset.
4. **Disaggregation - inheritance:** A characteristic of a parent entity is inherited by all child entities (for example best practices in respect of citation, applicable to an organisation, is inherited by all repositories operated by the organisation).

¹³ Developed in FAIR-IMPACT WP5, but not published in the final deliverable
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15534285>

Capturing and Harvesting Attributes Model

Automated methods are suitable for capturing repository attributes, but these must usually be supplemented with manually compiled information. The different sources of information for automatized information harvesting have already been identified above: (1) **self-hosted information**, (2) **registry-based information** and (3) **authority-based information**. In addition, (4) **expert-based information** provided by repository staff constitutes an essential source of knowledge, particularly with respect to information and services that are human-focused.

This results in a relatively simple conceptual model in which each source requires its own **specialized harvesting logic**. The model relies on established standards (e.g., RDF, DCAT) to parse and aggregate the collected information. In addition to harvesting logic, suitable processes for metadata transformation are required to ensure that data from different sources can be interpreted and aligned consistently.

A distinct **identifier harmonization process** ensures that entities and records originating from multiple sources are linked to unified, consistent identifiers. This process serves as a bridge between **metadata transformation and aggregation**, enabling coherent referencing and preventing duplication or fragmentation of identities across systems.

In addition to the automated harvesting approach, the model also incorporates **components for manual information collection and curation**. These components enable users or domain experts to enter, validate, or enrich metadata that cannot be automatically extracted, ensuring completeness and semantic accuracy.

Finally, the model incorporates an **aggregation layer** through which the collected, transformed, and harmonized information is registered and made accessible as part of an integrated framework.

Figure 6: Harvesting and Harmonisation Model

Guidance

The model developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC for CAT has been extended and refined in the OSTRAILS project respect of guidance associated with the principles, criteria, metrics, tests, and benchmarks for a specific 'motivation' (e.g. FAIR assessment, repository selection or appraisal, ...). This model is shown in Figure 7 and is published¹⁴ as the 'FAIR Guidance Vocabulary (FGV) – Core Ontology' for review within the OStrails project.

Figure 7: Guidance Model developed in OSTRAILS, and linked to CAT

The guidance model is currently being implemented as the basis of guidance for FAIR assessment in two projects that share the same implementation proof-of-concept¹⁵.

In broad terms, the guidance model allows us to link guidance from a large variety of sources to the ecosystem entities and the compliance assessment model for a specific context. In the case of EOSC EDEN, the guidance included into the model could address outputs such as the CPP, recommendations in respect of services and specifications, etc.

¹⁴ <https://ostrails.github.io/FAIR-Guidance-Vocabulary>

¹⁵ <https://fairassessment.dansdemo.nl/guidance>

The sources of guidance can be

- **Hosted locally:** guidance is recorded and maintained in the registry knowledge base.
- **Hosted externally,** in one of the following standard arrangements:
 - As an **external web page** resource, optionally making use of an annotation to refer to specific content¹⁶ and optionally but preferably referenced via a PID;
 - As an **API call** that returns a fragment of guidance as text, markdown, or HTML¹⁷;

The OSTRAILS project has also spent effort on defining the scope and types of guidance that would typically be available - the definitions are provided below.

- **Guidance:** General advice or direction provided to help decision-making, implementation, or problem-solving in a specific context. Also used as a collective noun for the following.
- **Framework:** A conceptual or structural foundation that organizes, aligns, and relates key components (such as goals, principles, processes, roles, and tools) within a particular domain or system of practice. It provides a coherent model for understanding and implementing policies, standards, procedures, and guidance.
- **Frequently Asked Questions** A curated list of common queries and clear, concise answers about a product, service, policy, or process.
- **Instructions:** Step-by-step directions that describe how to perform a specific task, process, or operation, typically in a procedural or operational context. The objective is to ensure accuracy and clarity.
- **Guideline:** Systematic instructions or practices designed to standardise activity or decision-making in specific situations.
- **Recommendation:** Suggestions or proposals for specific actions or practices based on evidence, expert opinion, or established norms.
- **Best Practice:** Proven methods or approaches that are widely accepted as the most effective in achieving desired outcomes.
- **Benchmark:** Quantifiable standards or reference points used to compare or evaluate performance, practices, or processes.
- **Specification:** Detailed descriptions of requirements, dimensions, materials, or processes for a product, service, or system to function as intended.
- **Procedure:** A defined and ordered series of steps or tasks to be performed to achieve a specific outcome or fulfill a process. It typically includes roles, conditions, inputs/outputs, and sometimes decision points.
- **Standard:** Documented agreements containing technical specifications or criteria to ensure consistent quality, safety, or interoperability. Standards are enforceable and typically developed by recognized authorities or organizations.

¹⁶ There are two mechanisms available for annotation: the [RDA Annotator](#) was developed by the RDA TIGER project, and can be repurposed to support semantic annotations of guidance content in EDEN, and [hypothes.is](#), which is a publicly available service but does not support semantic annotation.

¹⁷ This option is often implemented by helpdesk software.

While it is tempting to refine and improve this set of definitions, it is not directly in scope for EOSC EDEN, and the work in OSTRAILS, EOSC Data Commons, and specific funding proposals currently being adjudicated are all focused on this task. We recommend adopting these and maintaining synchronisation with any improvements made by the projects mentioned.

Description of Registry Entities and Relations

An overview of the main entities, or concepts and their relationships that will live in the EDEN Registry identified by their unambiguous IRI's is ongoing work and will be described as part of the EDEN Registry knowledgebase. Initially this will be focused around Repositories, their exposed Services and Attributes. Attributes can be grouped into Profiles. The IRI's will be mapped to the entities listed in the conceptual model described earlier in this document.

Appendix A: Attribute Profiles

The RDA TRSP WG has done substantial work in identifying, disambiguating, and mapping attribute lists from a number of sources¹⁸. Each of the sources represent a profile. These are listed in Table A.1, together with additional profile sources that are of interest to EOSC EDEN.

Work is in progress to analyse the outputs of EDEN WP2 and WP1 and to collate them with the attribute list in progress in the TRSP WG.

In addition, The FIDELIS project has published the TTRAM¹⁹, which will result in a separate profile of attributes, and a number of repositories have been added as prospective FIDELIS network members. Each of these repositories will likely already have attributes available from registries such as [re3data](#), [FAIRSharing](#), the [EOSC Resource Hub](#), and [COAR](#) (recently launched). A few may be advertising attributes using the [FAIRiCat](#) specification. A **composite of attributes** from these sources represent the attribute profile of a repository (“**Repository Profile**”).

Figure A.1 shows a partial view of the sources of attributes.

Figure A.1: Sources of Attribute Profiles.

Any profile can be compared to any other profile, for example, the profile of a given repository can be compared to the profile of CoreTrustSeal or the FIDELIS network. This serves as a primary determination of whether any subsequent actions (verification, review, assessment against a benchmark, computation of a metric, ...) can be performed.

¹⁸

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1PCPbuzZ7BQ0t2q_mkmb9IM6H1peCak3F9_JbDoXwg3c/edit?usp=sharing

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17157958>

The relations between profiles were identified early in the EOSC EDEN project and is summarised in Figure A.2.

Figure A.2: Proposed Structuring of Repository and Community Attribute Profiles

The structure proposed in Figure A.2 results in several benefits:

- From an inventory of attributes, defined as inclusively as possible and accommodating a wide scope of case studies, it is possible to define multiple organising perspectives through grouping, sub-setting and classification - creating a **Community Profile**. The FIDELIS TTRAM, for example, is equivalent to a community profile, or could result in multiple profiles for more than one perspective or motivation. CoreTrustSeal, FAIR, and EOSC Node onboarding requirements are all examples of community profiles.
- Comparing a community profile to a repository profile is equivalent to an assessment or appraisal, and modes of verification can be diversified to accommodate audited assessments (such as ISO), peer-reviewed assessments (such as CoreTrustSeal) or self-assessment - with or without evidence.
- Because the 'repository' profile can be generalised as an 'actor' profile, it is easy to formulate equivalent profiles for other actors (such as TRSPs or software platforms), and to differentiate between e.g. data repositories and software repositories.

- Selecting one or more repositories or services on the basis of a set of arbitrary attributes is effectively applying an ad-hoc 'community' profile, with benchmarks determined informally.
- Tests can be determined to compare repository profiles to community profiles or to standard profiles, and community profiles can also be compared to the standard profile.

The attributes themselves can be organised into groups, hierarchies, or even graph-like structures with a parent-child relationship. We provide a few examples of such multi-level profiles:

- The [Global Open Research Commons](#) (GORC) elements, features and attributes provides an organising framework for the attributes associated with research commons implementations, and the GORC attributes map to (is a subset of) the standard attribute set.
- The [TRUST Principles](#) indirectly imply a list of attributes associated with each principle, as elaborated by the RDA TRSP WG.
- The TRSP itself has defined a [graph-like hierarchy of attributes](#)²⁰, loosely based on and extending the main principles in TRUST and its details.

²⁰ An attribute can be linked in more than one branch of the hierarchy.

Appendix B: Verifying Attributes

This discussion is based on ongoing work in the [RDA TRSP Working Group](#) and will become citable once the WG has published a white paper on the subject. This is currently in preparation.

Figure B.1 describes the typical options available for verification of attributes ('asserted values' as defined by FAIR-IMPACT).

Figure B.1: Degrees of Assurance in Performance Appraisal

In the figure, the sources of and motivation for appraisal and its associated content is categorised as follows:

- The most broadly scoped source would be informal but widely recognised desirable features and characteristics of repositories. There are many sources of these attributes - for example attributes defined by [GORC](#), or the attributes defined by [DRAWG](#).
- There are best practices and recommendations in respect of attributes, their definitions, and more importantly, what constitutes broadly accepted norms for the values of these attributes or the content of documentation provided as evidence that an attribute is available. As an example
 - An attribute may describe the metadata harvesting service(s) offered by a repository.
 - The attribute may be defined as ideally providing local API URLs for standardised API implementations from a list, for example a registry containing entries for common implementations such as [OAI-PMH](#), a [SPARQL](#) endpoint, and [CS/W](#).

- Best practice or a recommendation might indicate that OAI-PMH is preferred for a specific context.
- Community benchmarks may further constrain the acceptable values for an attribute, for example by indicating that in order to be a part of the FIDELIS Network, an API endpoint for an OAI-PMH service must be indicated.
- Verifying the assertion that a specific endpoint has been implemented can be done via one of three mechanisms:
 - **Self-assessment**, which does not require any additional verification of the assertion.
 - Self-assessment with **public benchmarking and evidence**, for example by providing evidence that an OAI-PMH endpoint is functional by publishing availability data.
 - **Assessment by a third party**, which involves audit or review of an assertion.
- The mechanism whereby an assertion can be verified can be one of several, which vary in respect of reproducibility. These mechanisms were analysed and defined in detail in the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Model²¹, and the options are defined in more detail below. Some of these verification mechanisms involve manual or automated tests and a metric. In the case of OAI-PMH endpoint verification, these might be:
 - A metric that measures whether the asserted endpoint conforms to the OAI-PMH specification, and whether it is available for harvesting with a minimum uptime.
 - Tests that determine OAI-PMH specification compliance.
 - Tests that determine availability.
 - The benchmark could be:
 - Specification compliance: Go/ No Go, i.e. the metric fails if the endpoint is not specification-compliant.
 - If it is compliant, the second part of the benchmark determines if availability is equal to or exceeds a norm, for example 98% uptime on a moving annual basis.

Not all attributes are verified by reproducible and properly documented tests, and the options described in Table B.1 have been identified in the FAIRCORE4EOSC CAT Model. Suggested refinements are shown in purple text.

Table B.1: Metric Typology and Typical Benchmarks

Metric Type	Description	Approach to Metric Definition	Typical Benchmark
Open Review	No guidelines are present, and reviewers make a completely subjective and independent conclusion about performance.	The metric is undocumented, the reviewer makes a subjective 'measurement' of performance	The assessor determines whether performance is acceptable or not based on tacit knowledge and experience.
Guided Review	Guidance on how to approach assessment of compliance is available	The metric is documented in the sense that the assessor is advised on which	The assessor determines whether performance across the typical considerations is

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067253>

		considerations are in scope for a subjective evaluation of performance, and the expected result is not always documented.	acceptable or not based on knowledge and experience and interpretation of the guideline.
Benchmarked Review	As for guided review, but it is possible to select a level of compliance by matching with described performance or examples	The metric is documented in the sense that the assessor is advised on which considerations apply to a subjective evaluation of performance and the result is not always documented. It is possible to map a subjective assessment to a defined level of performance or maturity	The benchmark describes which of the considerations are considered to be important, non-negotiable, or optional, and the assessment is made by the assessor based on experience and mapping of subjective considerations to the benchmarks - which may describe recommended or best practices.
Subjective Ranking	Assessment by assigning a ranking to a compliance claim or description (subjectively). Often employed when assessment is competitive - for example for grant applications.	The metric is documented in the sense that the assessor is presented with one or more considerations and ranks them subjectively.	The assessor determines whether performance across the typical considerations is acceptable or not based on tacit knowledge and experience.
Binary	True or false, for example by determining whether there is evidence supporting a compliance claim	The metric is documented, based on reproducible tests, and it is clear what will constitute a true or false result when considering performance across one or more tests.	The benchmark determines whether performance is acceptable, but it is often a trivial case - true being acceptable ('Pass'), and false being unacceptable ('Fail'). A benchmark may be more applicable in cases of multiple tests for the same metric.
Measured or Computed Value	Measuring objectively using an instrument and/ or a method (test), result is a defined variable - for example 'number of employees'	The metric is documented, including reproducible tests, and it is clear how a value will be computed for performance across one or more tests.	The benchmark determines whether performance is acceptable, often with a mapping to benchmark categories.
Composite Assessment	Aggregation of a collection/ hierarchy of weighted and normalised measures. Includes ranking, multicriteria analysis, and analytic hierarchy methods.	A mechanism is provided whereby a metric is composed of other metrics and/ or tests, and the combination of results is based on some form of weighted aggregation. Simple methods sum the results over several tests and/ or metrics and implicitly weight all equally.	The benchmark determines whether performance is acceptable, often with a mapping to benchmark categories.

Objective Ranking	Ranking against peers through quantitative methods, e.g. pairwise comparison	The test method assumes that all instances of a population are measured together, or measurements for all exist. By comparing an individual instance against each other instance and selecting the best performing instance, an objective ranking is obtained. Pairwise comparisons are also often combined for more than one assessor or observer.	The benchmark determines whether performance is acceptable, often with a mapping to benchmark categories.
Classification	Supervised or unsupervised classification based on ML mechanisms or heuristics	A number of test values or characteristics of a subject are combined into a classification heuristic, often by developing such a heuristic from learning examples. Neural networks for classification are one example of such an approach.	The benchmark determines whether performance is acceptable, often with a mapping to benchmark categories.

Not all of these approaches result in reproducible outcomes, and while reproducibility (by a third party) is an ideal, it may not be necessary in all circumstances. Transparency (how an outcome was reached) may also be required in many instances. With these considerations in mind, some approaches listed above are less appropriate.

Moreover, not all approaches are automatable or machine-actionable, and since scalability for assessment is a major bottleneck in quality assurance processes, approaches that can be automated are more attractive.

Based on these considerations, Table B.2 summarises our classification of the approaches listed in Table B.1.

Table B.2: Metric Typology and Design Considerations

Metric Type	Reproducibility	Transparency	Automation
Open Review	Low	Low	No
Guided Review	Low	Low	No
Benchmarked Review	Medium	Medium	No
Subjective Ranking	Medium	Medium	No
Binary	High	High	Yes
Measured or Computed Value	High	High	Yes
Composite Assessment	High	High	Yes
Objective Ranking	Medium	High	Maybe
Classification	High ²²	Medium	Yes

²² Depending on model quality and training